

From The Desk of Guest Editor....

Is it the Right Time to Change the Education System in India?

Education is what remains after one has forgotten what one has learned in school.

Albert Einstein

Education is one of the vital services that a modern state is expected to provide to its people. From Aristotle to APJ Abdul Kalam, every famous personality has time and again stressed on the importance of education in our lives. It enables and empowers people, it provides one with diverse knowledge, expertise, skills and helps develop the essential skills in life. Education equips people with basic values and ethics in life to make them sharp and clever enough to deal with the real world. We have progressed with time; however, we still have not been able to move away from rote learning.

The Indian education system needs a total overhauling. More than 80% of the courses in our education system do not provide us any kind of skill, it is only mugging and rote the chapters no practical knowledge, no research projects. The machinery of mass-producing graduates and scholars with zero analytical thinking is a current system. Our education system is turning us into mental slaves and the proof is our exams. It is geared towards teaching and testing knowledge at every level as opposed to teaching skills. "Give a man a fish and you feed him one day, teach him how to catch fishes and you feed him for a lifetime." I believe that if you teach a man a skill, you enable him for a lifetime. Knowledge is largely forgotten after the semester exam is over. Still, year after year Indian students focus on cramming information. The best crammers are rewarded by the system. This is one of the fundamental flaws of our education system. Our education system rarely rewards what deserves highest academic accolades. Deviance is discouraged. Risk taking is mocked. Our testing and marking systems need to be built to recognize original contributions, in form of creativity, problem solving, valuable original research and innovation. If we could do this successfully Indian education system would have changed overnight.

Education is a place where we can broaden our knowledge and showcase our creativity but now the definition of education is completely different. None of the students are studying happily, they all are feeling it as a burden and becoming stressed day by day due to the amount of work given by their teachers. Here the workload has increased and the ability to show their innovation has decreased. Students are being given projects but they are not doing it in a correct way i.e. not using their creativity. They are just copying the information from the resources and not gaining any knowledge from it. Memorising is no learning; the biggest flaw in our education system is perhaps that it incentivizes memorizing above originality. Despite the fact that every individual has different learning abilities, some are visual learners, some are auditory learners and some learn from experience. Indian education system is built on the presumption that if something is good for one individual, it is good for all. If one massive monolithic education system has to provide education to everyone, then there is no option but to assume that one size fits all. Everybody is genius if you judge a fish by its ability to climb a tree, it will live its whole life believing that it is stupid.

It has been observed in past time that mediocre or average students have excelled as great Entrepreneur or successful professionals. **Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam** our former president has very rightly said **"Some of the brightest minds in the country can be found on the last benches of the classroom"**.

We need to restore our primitive Indian Gurukul education system which was the backbone of India. We have to quit focusing only on degrees and numbers. There is no focus on merit and quality education. Creating a few more schools or allowing hundreds of colleges and private universities to mushroom is not going to solve the crisis of education in India. And a crisis it is – we are in a country where people are spending their parent's life savings and borrowed money on education – and even then not getting standard education, and struggling to find employment of their choice. In this country, millions of students are victim of an unrealistic, pointless, mindless rat race. The mind numbing competition and rote learning do not only crush the creativity and originality of millions of Indian students every year, it also drives brilliant students to commit suicide.

The institutions must lay their emphasis on conceptual learning rather than rote learning. This will enhance the retention rate of the education imparted. Emphasis should not be on free and compulsory education. However, the emphasis should be only on quality education to make an individual a true human being. Here, I would like to quote **C.S Lewis** statement- **Education without values, as useful as it is, seems rather to make man a more clever devil.** So I conclude by saying **"Intelligence plus character is the goal of true education"**